

DIETARY PREVENTION OF CANCER

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Abstract. This article provides information on the nutrition of cancer patients and the role of diet in cancer prevention. Cancer and its treatment are a very special situation, and a cancer patient needs special nutrition. On the one hand, the disease itself, on the other hand, the methods used to treat it cause anorexia. In addition, both cancer and drugs disrupt the absorption of a number of nutrients, so adherence to the principles of proper nutrition is an important measure for both the prevention and treatment of cancer and other tumor diseases.

Key words: nutrition, vegetarian nutrition, antitumor diet, cruciferous vegetables, carotenoids.

Relevance. Currently, about 200 factors that cause malignant tumors have been identified. Among them, poor nutrition is in the first place. About a third of all types of cancer, or rather, 35%, are associated with this factor. In second place is smoking. It causes 30% of malignant tumors. At first glance, the risk of cancer can be significantly reduced by eating right and quitting smoking. However, for many, it is quite difficult to make such sacrifices for the sake of their health.

Cancer is one of the leading causes of death worldwide. However, current research suggests that 30-50% of cancers can be prevented by making simple lifestyle changes, such as eating a healthy diet. In addition to reducing the risk of cancer, a healthy diet can help you achieve an ideal weight and improve your mood. Nutrition plays a crucial role in the prevention and treatment of cancer. It is an integral part of treatment.

Normalization of excess body weight and factors of nutrition optimization are of fundamental importance. At the same time, the results of long-term use of strict diets with restriction of caloric content and biological completeness of the diet are unpredictable and often one has to deal with severe consequences of such diets. The role of vegetarian diet in cancer prevention is debated. Vegetarians

have higher levels of antioxidant vitamins and microelements (selenium, zinc, copper) in their blood. The most important circumstance to consider when formulating vegetarian diets is the inadequacy of the amino acid composition of plant proteins. The composition of many vegetarian dishes in the food culture of various nations is selected empirically: a mixture of corn and legumes, rice and soybeans.

It should be noted that the consumption of green tea and plant foods in general is high among the peoples of the Asian continent. This explains the so-called Asian advantage - a significant (several times) decrease in the incidence of colon cancer, breast cancer and tumors of other localizations in the Asian region compared to the countries of Europe and North America.

The basic principles of preventive nutrition aimed at preventing cancer can be presented as follows:

1. Reduce fat consumption to 30% of total calorie intake and completely eliminate foods containing large amounts of refractory fats;
2. Fractional nutrition (five meals or more);
3. Increase consumption of fruits, vegetables and grains;
4. Limiting intake of refined carbohydrates;
5. Limiting meat consumption, especially fatty meat and meat that has been fried or smoked;
6. Moderate consumption of salty and spicy foods;
7. Moderate alcohol consumption.

The author of the first anti-tumor diet belongs to the Dutch doctor Cornelius Moerman. The main provisions of the diet can be presented as follows:

1. Tumor cells receive energy primarily from glucose, so the glycemic curve must be maintained at a low physiological level by limiting or eliminating simple carbohydrates from the diet (including confectionery, honey), and products made from premium flour.

2. Drastically reduce the consumption of animal proteins to create a deficiency of essential amino acids and thereby reduce protein synthesis by tumor cells.

3. Eat a predominantly plant-based diet, whole grain and bran products. The diet should contain enough fiber and products with specific anti-carcinogenic activity (garlic, green tea, cruciferous vegetables, carotenoids), vitamin products and freshly prepared juices (beetroot, carrot, blackcurrant, apple, cabbage). Include antioxidant vitamins, citric acid, iodine and sulfur preparations in the diet.

4. To introduce calcium into the body and correct intestinal function, use low-fat dairy products (kefir, yogurt), combining them with cultures of beneficial microorganisms.

5. To saturate the body with ω -3 acids, you need to consume nuts (3-5 pieces per day), olive and flaxseed oil, and sea fish (at least 3 times a week).

6. Drink only artesian (preferably melted) water. You should use it to prepare teas, decoctions, infusions.

7. Certain foods and supplements should be limited, in particular salt. In the absence of anemia, red meat, liver, and iron-containing preparations (which may be part of vitamin and mineral complexes) should be excluded from the diet. Complexes containing B vitamins should not be used without control. Exceeding physiological doses of these compounds can promote tumor growth.

8. You should refrain from drinking coffee and alcohol.

The following recommendations can be formulated for individuals who want to adhere to a preventive anti-tumor diet:

1. Avoid excess fat consumption.

The maximum amount of free fat is 1 tablespoon of vegetable oil per day (preferably olive oil). Avoid other fats, especially animal fats.

2. Avoid fats from going rancid.

Do not use fats that have been reused for frying and overheated during cooking. In extreme cases, use fats that are resistant to heat: butter or olive oil. It is better to add fats not at the time, but after cooking the products.

Buy nuts only in shell. Do not eat peeled seeds that have been stored for a long time. Buy oil in opaque bottles or hard jars.

3. Cook with a little salt and do not add salt to food.

4. Limit sugar and other refined carbohydrates.

5. Limit your meat consumption.

Replace some meat with plant proteins (legumes), fish (preferably small deep-sea varieties), eggs (no more than 3 per week), low-fat dairy products.

When eating meat, consider its "value" – in descending order: lean white meat, rabbit, veal, free-range chicken (not broiler), lean red meat, fatty meat.

Avoid sausages, hot dogs, as well as grilled meat, smoked meat and fish.

6. Steam, bake or simmer foods with a minimum amount of water, which you also consume. Avoid burnt foods.

7. Eat whole grain cereals, breads enriched with dietary fiber. Do not peel vegetables: just wash them thoroughly with a brush.

8. Use spring water, let the water settle, or purify it in other ways.

Drink herbal infusions and fruit juices instead of tea. Try not to drink carbonated drinks with artificial additives.

9. Don't overeat. Eat when you feel hungry.

10. Do not abuse alcohol.

Conclusion. Of course, it is very difficult to blame this or that product or food additive for the occurrence or development of oncological diseases, but our diet can often become a mechanism that triggers the formation of tumors. Nutrition should be complete, varied, but moderate. It is also necessary to adhere to a healthy lifestyle and abandon harmful habits. Most importantly, do not consume products with a long shelf life and expired dates

References:

1. Yazıcı, O., Özdemir, N. (2018). Meme Kanserinde Epidemiyolojik Veriler, Risk Faktörleri, Risk Azaltıcı Yaklaşımlar. Türkiye Klinikleri Tıbbi Onkoloji-Özel Konular, 11(1), 1-7.
2. Siegel, R.L.; Miller, K.D.; Fuchs, H.E.; Jemal, A. Cancer statistics, 2022. CA Cancer J. Clin. 2022, 72, 7-33.].
3. Парпиева, О. Р., Эрматова, Г. А., Камалова, Д. А., & Якубов, А. (2024). КОРРЕЛЯЦИОННАЯ СВЯЗЬ МЕЖДУ ПИТАНИЕМ И СОСТОЯНИЕМ ЗДОРОВЬЯ ЖЕНЩИН РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. JOURNAL OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY, 7(6), 4-10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11634575>
4. Парпиева, О. Р. (2023). КЎКРАК БЕЗИ САРАТОНИ ҲАҚИДА ТУШУНЧА. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education. Social Science & Humanities, 11(3), 446-454.
5. Parpiyeva Odinaxon Rakhmanovna. (2022). Nutrition and diet in breast cancer. Texas Journal of Medical Science, 7, 27-30. <https://doi.org/10.62480/tjms.2022.vol7.pp27-30>
6. Parpiyeva O.R. - ASSESSMENT OF THE MAIN INDICATORS OF BREAST CANCER IN THE TERRITORIES OF THE FERGANA REGION//New Day in Medicine 4(78)2025 1121-1126 https://newdayworldmedicine.com/en/new_day_medicine/4-78-2025
7. Parpiyeva, O. R., & Mirzajonova, E. T. (2022). The role of psycho-oncology in the treatment of cancer patients. Texas Journal of Medical Science, 9, 14-17.
8. Normatova, S. A., & Parpiyeva, O. R. (2024). ASSESSMENT OF THE ROLE OF RISK FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF BREAST CANCER. THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH, 2(21), 74-78. <https://interonconf.org/index.php/taare/article/view/10467>
9. Parpiyeva, O. (2023). KO'KRAK BEZI SARATONI BILAN KASALLANGAN AYOLLAR OVQATLANISHINI KORREKTSIYALASHNI ILMIIY ASOSLASH. MAVZUSI

ВО 'УСНА АДАБИЙОТЛАР ТАHLИЛИ. Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук, 3(12), 168-177.

10. Normatova Sh.A., & Parpiyeva O.R. (2023). AYOLLARDA KO'KRAK BEZI SARATONINI ERTA ANIQLASHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUV. В actacamu: Тт. 2 2023 (Выпуски 2181-4155, с. 116). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7924839>

11. Эрматова, Г. А., Парпиева, О. Р., Якубов, А., & Камалова, Д. А. (2024). ПРИВЫЧКИ ЗДОРОВОГО ПИТАНИЯ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ПОВСЕДНЕВНОЙ ЖИЗНИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 12(5), 1221-1228.

12. Парпиева, О. Р., & Назарова, Д. (2024). ПРИНЦИПЫ ДИЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ ОНКОЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ. SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI, 7(12), 82-85.

